

Repository content description

Associated with the IMPASTO project - <https://impastopr.net>

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The image files contained in this repository present research results from the regional seasonal climate model numerical experiments carried out in the project, that explored sensitivity of seasonal regional climate ensemble prediction to stochastic representation of model errors associated with physical parameterizations using the Stochastically Perturbed Parameterization Tendency (SPPT) scheme. The model used for the experiments is the research version of the NMMB model (Janic et al., 2001; Janic, 2003; Janic and Gall, 2012) provided by the Faculty of Physics University in Belgrade. The data used to produce the graphics are available for download at <http://haos.ff.bg.ac.rs/IMPASTO/>) without any restrictions.

The results displayed in the figures are associated with the four numerical experiments briefly described in Table 1.

Table 1 Seasonal sensitivity experiments with the regional model.

Experiment label	Experiment configuration	Ensemble ICs and BCs	Stochastic scheme	Ensemble size
CO	Single seasonal simulation using the NMMB model without SPPT scheme. The ICs and BCs were derived from the ECMWF seasonal system forecast that was initiated using the operational best analysis	No	No	1
NS	Ensemble seasonal simulations using the NMMB model without SPPT scheme and the ECMWF seasonal ensemble forecast data : the global ensemble analysis for the initial conditions and ensemble forecast for lateral boundary conditions	Yes	No	12
ST	Ensemble seasonal simulations using the deterministic ECMWF seasonal forecast data, as for the experiment labeled CO, but with the SPPT scheme activated in the regional model	No	Yes	12
CS	Ensemble seasonal simulations using the SPPT in the regional model and the ECMWF seasonal ensemble forecast data (the ensemble initial and boundary conditions as in the experiment labeled NS)	Yes	Yes	12

The results presented by the images in this repository are grouped into 7 image sets (7 files), corresponding to different experiments and statistical diagnostics

1. comparative_stats_all_experiments
2. ns experiment monthly stats
3. ns experiment weekly stats
4. cs experiment monthly stats
5. cs experiment weekly stats
6. st experiment monthly stats
7. st experiment weekly stats

The '**comparative_stats**' set contains 5 figures with cumulative statistical results of spatially and temporally averaged ensemble standard deviation and difference between the ensemble mean (the experiments NS, ST and CS) and the deterministic control experiment (CO) described in Table 1. The spatial averaging was performed for the entire integration horizontal domain and also subsets of grid points with presence of precipitation as determined by the control experiment. The temporal averaging was performed for monthly and weekly periods within the seasonal integration period (6 months). These diagnostics are presented for the following 5 physical quantities : temperature and humidity at 2 meters (respectively labeled in the following t2m and q2m), two wind components at 10 meters (labeled u10 and v10) and 6-hourly accumulated precipitation (labeled acprec).

The remaining sets (2-7) contain 2D maps of time mean (monthly or weekly) of control solution (the experiment CO in Table 1)
ensemble_mean (for the experiments NS, ST and CS in Table 1)
differences between the ensemble_mean and control
ensemble standard deviation (for the experiments NS, ST and CS in Table 1)

The data displayed in the maps are for the following physical quantities : acprec , t2m, q2m, u10, v10, slp (sea level pressure), z500 and z850 (respectively geopotential height at 500 and 850 mb pressure levels)

Key for interpreting file names, using t2m as example

t2m_cow.1.png control (co) averaged over 1 week (w) for the first week (1)
t2m_emw.1.png ensemble mean (em)
t2m_diffw.1.png difference between ensemble mean and control (diff)
t2m_esdw.1.png ensemble standard deviation (esd)

the same file naming key applies for monthly averages but m is used instead of w
t2m_com.1.png control (co) averaged over 1 month (m) for the first month (1)

NMMB model references

Janjic Z., J.P. Gerrity, Jr. and S. Nickovic, 2001, An alternative approach to nonhydrostatic modeling. Monthly Weather Review, 129, 1164-1178.

Janjic Z., 2003, A Nonhydrostatic Model Based on a New Approach. Meteorology and Atmospheric Physics, 82, 271-285. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00703-001-0587-6>

Janjic, Z., and Gall, R. L., 2012, Scientific documentation of the NCEP nonhydrostatic multiscale model on the B grid (NMMB). Part 1 Dynamics (No. NCAR/TN-489+STR). University Corporation for Atmospheric Research. doi:10.5065/D6WH2MZX